

Further Studies on Fluoroberyllic Acid

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Starting with fluoroberyllic acid a number of hitherto unknown fluoroberyllates have been prepared. These include sodium and potassium acid fluoroberyllates. A nitrosyl derivative of fluoroberyllic acid has also been prepared. Besides a number of additive compounds have been prepared from the acid and organic amines.

Fluoroberyllates have hitherto been prepared by dissolving oxide or carbonate of beryllium in hydrofluoric acid, with requisite quantities of hydroxide, oxide or carbonate of other metals. Complete neutralisation of the acid, however, causes precipitation of basic salts of sparingly soluble fluorides. Excess of hydrofluoric acid, on the other hand often leads to formation of acid fluorides of metals. Ghosh¹ succeeded in preparing chromic fluoroberyllate by keeping the solution slightly acid with acetic acid. It appears that in the preparation of a fluoroberyllate an acid medium is desirable. Boral and Ray² have recently shown that the fluoroberyllate ion is very stable in acid solution upto pH 5.5. Isolation of free fluoroberyllic acid³ has opened up a new and very convenient method for the preparation of fluoroberyllates. Treatment of this acid with oxide or carbonate of a metal will easily form its fluoroberyllate. Care should be taken to avoid complete neutralisation of the acid. Recently several new fluoroberyllates have been obtained by this process. The acid being dibasic both normal and acid salts have been prepared. This paper deals with the preparation of some acid fluoroberyllates and normal fluoroberyllates by making use of fluoroberyllic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluoroberyllic Acid : Fluoroberyllic acid used was prepared by the ion exchange method³.

Organic Amines : Organic amines were distilled before use in the preparations. The following organic amines were used (1) Aniline, (2) Pyridine, (3) Quinoline, (4) Triethyl amine, (5) Ethylene diamine.

Acid Fluoroberyllates of Potassium and Sodium : Calculated amounts of potassium fluoroberyllate and 12(N) fluoroberyllic acid were mixed together and dissolved by gentle stirring. The solution so prepared was kept in a desiccator over conc. H₂SO₄. The crystals formed were filtered, washed with ice-cold water, dried and analysed.

The sodium acid fluoroberyllate was likewise prepared by adding sodium fluoroberyllate to 12N fluoroberyllic acid.

Both sodium and potassium acid fluoroberyllates are white crystals easily soluble in water, the solutions in each case were found to be acidic to litmus, in sharp contrast to solutions of normal salts of fluoroberyllic acid. On heating the dry salts to redness both sodium and potassium acid fluoroberyllates change to a mixture of beryllium fluoride and potassium or sodium fluoride. From X-ray analysis it has been observed that the acid fluoroberyllates are isomorphous with the respective acid sulphates.

Acid Fluoroberyllates of Organic Bases : To ascertain the possibility of direct combination of fluoroberyllic acid with organic bases, titrations were carried out conductometrically and potentiometrically. For convenience only liquid amines were considered. The results were plotted in graphs. The breaks in the curves revealed the feasibility of such direct combinations in unimolar proportions.

Aniline Fluoroberyllate ($C_6H_5NH_2$) H_2BeF_4 : In 1 : 1 molar proportion fluoroberyllic acid (6*N*) and aniline were mixed together. The solution was evaporated in vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . The yellowish crystals obtained were redissolved in water. On adding alcohol to this aqueous solution colourless crystals of aniline fluoroberyllate separated. The substance is soluble in water and the solution is acidic to litmus.

Pyridine Fluoroberyllate (C_5H_5N) H_2BeF_4 : Calculated amounts of fluoroberyllic acid (6*N*) and pyridine were mixed together in molar proportion 1 : 1. The solution from which an oil separated was then evaporated in vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . Needle-shaped crystals obtained were filtered, washed with absolute alcohol, dried in air. The substance is fairly soluble in water, the solution turns blue litmus red. It is insoluble in acetone.

Quinoline Fluoroberyllate (C_9H_7N) H_2BeF_4 : Fluoroberyllic acid solution (6*N*) and quinoline in molar proportion 1 : 1 were mixed. The resulting mixture was allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator. The crystals obtained were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. The substance was found to be soluble in water but not in acetone or ether.

Triethylamine Fluoroberyllate (C_2H_5) $_3NH_2BeF_4$: In molar proportion 1 : 1 fluoroberyllic acid (6*N*) was mixed with triethylamine. The mixture was allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 . The crystals separated were dissolved in water and reprecipitated with alcohol. The precipitate was filtered and dried.

Hexamine fluoroberyllate (CH_2) $_6N_4H_2BeF_4$: Hexamine was dissolved in dil. acetic acid. The solution obtained was treated with fluoroberyllic acid in water solution. A white precipitate was formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed with very dil. acetic acid, water and then with alcohol and dried.

Benzidine fluoroberyllate : Benzidine was dissolved in dilute acetic acid. To a part of this solution an aqueous solution of fluoroberyllic acid was added in the cold. A heavy white precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed in succession with dilute acetic acid, water and alcohol. The dried product was then analysed.

Ethylenediamine fluoroberyllate ($NH_2CH_2CH_2NH_2$) H_2BeF_4 : In molar proportion 1 : 1 fluoroberyllic acid (6*N*) was treated with ethylenediamine at 0°. The solution was crystallised in a desiccator. The crystals were redissolved in water and reprecipitated with alcohol, filtered and dried.

Nitrosyl fluoroberyllate : Fairly concentrated, fluoroberyllic acid (17*N*) was taken in a polythene conical flask fitted with a cork through which passed two polythene tubes one of which was connected to a Woulfe's bottle generating oxides of nitrogen from copper-turnings and conc. nitric acid, while the other served as an outlet.

Oxides of nitrogen were passed through the fluoroberyllic acid for several hours. During this operation the acid in the flask was cooled by ice. Thereafter the acid was transferred to a polythene beaker and kept in a desiccator in the cold. After several days colourless crystals were obtained. These were filtered, washed rapidly with ice cold water, dried and analysed.

TABLE 1

Results of Analysis

Compounds	% Na or % K		% F		% Bc		% N	
	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Cal.
Potassium Acid Fluoroberyllate KHBef ₄	31.02	31.23	61.20	60.80	7.01	7.20	—	—
Sodium Acid Fluoroberyllate NaHBef ₄ .H ₂ O	18.67	18.88	60.12	59.84	6.90	7.08	—	—
Aniline Fluoroberyllate (C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂)H ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	41.80	42.20	4.90	5.00	7.67	7.80
Pyridine Fluoroberyllate (C ₅ H ₅ N)H ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	45.30	45.70	5.33	5.42	8.28	8.40
Quinoline Fluoroberyllate (C ₉ H ₇ N)H ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	34.59	35.18	4.00	4.12	6.28	6.48
Triethylamine Fluoroberyllate (C ₂ H ₅) ₃ NH ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	40.12	40.40	4.90	4.70	6.90	7.10
Hexamine Fluoroberyllate (CH ₂) ₆ N ₄ H ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	34.30	33.48	4.06	3.96	24.10	24.60
Benzidine Fluoroberyllate (C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ H ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	27.50	28.04	3.19	3.30	10.60	10.30
Ethylene diamine Fluoroberyllate (NH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂)H ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	36.15	36.40	4.28	4.35	18.70	19.00
Nitrosyl Fluoroberyllate (NO) ₂ BeF ₄	—	—	52.54	52.40	6.13	6.20	19.19	19.31

Method of Analysis : Beryllium was estimated by precipitating as Be(OH)₂ and igniting to BeO. For estimating fluorine, beryllium was precipitated as Be(OH)₂ with ammonia and removed by filtration. In the filtrate, fluorine was estimated by precipitation as CaF₂ in ammoniacal medium and weighing as CaF₂ after ignition. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method or by Dumas method.

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